

EDUCATION AND COVID 19 IN THE LENS OF WORKING STUDENTS OF LANTON HIGH SCHOOL: BASIS FOR PROJECT POSITIVE (PEER OUTREACHING OF WORKING STUDENTS AND SPECIALIZED INTERVAL OF TIME SCHEDULE TO INTENSIFY AND VALIDATE EDUCATION IN THIS NEW NORMAL)

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ABSTRACT

This Action Research is materialized with the vision to help the working students of Lanton High School. This study aims to elucidate the education process during the COVID 19 pandemic in the lens of the working students of Lanton High School. Specifically, it sought to answer the scope of work of the working students of Lanton High School in terms of their time schedule and nature of work. This action research looked also for the overall experiences of the working students during the new normal especially on the module distribution, passing of answer sheets and accomplishing the SLMs/ SSLMs. The design of the study is phenomenological in nature. There were fifteen (15) working students who were the respondents of the study and were chosen through a purposive and snowball sampling method. Through a thorough analysis, the study revealed that women working students tend to have domestic job with a very flexible time while men working students engaged in hard manual labor having an imposed time to conform. These working students still believed that education is vital in the time of pandemic; that they can still continue studying even they working and teachers and classmates are still part of learning even on distance learning. These were three (3) themes that come out after the interview. The result of this Action Research is the formulation of Project POSITIVE (Peer Outreaching of working students and Specialized Interval of Time schedule to Intensify and Validate Education in this New Normal).

Keywords: *pandemic, module, working students, action research, new normal, Philippines*

INTRODUCTION

When the whole nation was placed into community quarantine, everybody was not prepared for such. Hence, many of us were affected physically, emotionally and even psychologically. Several things have been shifted to things that we are not used to, brought about by this COVID 19 Pandemic. One of the most affected sectors in the society is the educational system of the country. The Department of Education (DepEd) developed a Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan (BE-LCP) through the DepEd Order No. 18, s. 2020 otherwise known as the Policy Guidelines for the Provision of Learning Resources in the Implementation of the Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan. The BE-LCP ensures the delivery of quality, relevant and liberating education for all its learners. Further, this is also in consonance with the 1987 Constitution which states in Article XIV Sections 1 “The state shall protect and promote the right of all citizens to quality education at all levels, and shall take appropriate steps to make such education accessible to all.” And Section 2 (1) “Establish, maintain and support a complete, adequate and integrated system of education relevant to the needs of the people and society” (2) “Establish and maintain a system of free public education in the elementary and high school levels.” With this, different learning modalities were implemented. These modalities are modular distance learning (MDL), radio-based instruction (BRI), TV-based instruction (TVBI), online learning and blended learning.

Lanton High School, as situated outside the city proper, having consolidated the results of the Learner Enrolment and Survey Form (LESF) during the remote enrolment opted to go on printed modular distance learning. Though the process of learning is a new paradigm for the students, majority have managed their learning style well. Processes of distributing of modules and retrieval of answer sheets have been evidently observed in school. Yet, there are still those who cannot cope with the scheduled time for distributing and retrieval processes.

Since that students are not permitted to go to school, there are some who have engaged themselves into jobs in order to assist their parents with financial burden. As a result, they tend to pass their answer sheets late given that they can only accomplish their self-learning modules at night or during their vacant time.

This time of pandemic, where other adults lost their jobs, students may go into a sort of income generating practices. Tsurugano, et al. (2021) noted in their research that the financial instability is severely affecting their academic performance and potentially their health. Students' maximum focus and study productivity are at risk if this issue arises (Chang & Fang, 2020). As to the research conducted by Rotas and Cahapay (2020), students expressed challenges in striking a balance between their home obligations and distance learning, even if living at home may provide comfort. It maintains their time apart. Students also expressed concern about how their schedules for remote learning interfere

with their domestic obligations. This result is consistent with Matswetu et al., (2013), in which Zimbabwean students encountered financial difficulties when enrolled in a remote learning program. Notably, because of an unprecedented economic closure during the outbreak, financial difficulties for low-income families in the Philippines have started to deteriorate (Adele, 2020).

There are significant obstacles in the planning, implementation, and assessment systems of educational institutions, especially in the Philippines. On a more positive side, though, the pandemic gave the nation the chance to modernize its methods of delivering education and focus on cutting-edge technologies (Toquero, 2020).

Given the current circumstances, an intervention intended for students who work for a living must be put into place. Two more essential performance indicators will be covered. The access comes first. Continuing with the pandemic, (a) dropout rates are high in many nations and prolonged disengagement may result in an even higher rate (Gayeta, 2020). Additionally, the quality of their education will increase if this program is appropriately executed for working students during this period when face-to-face instruction is forbidden.

There were 405,644 household members in General Santos City that were at least 15 years old in 2015. Of this total, about three out of every five individuals (57.6%) worked for pay in the twelve months before to the census. Men made up 66.3 percent of those who engaged in gainful activity over the previous 12-month reference period, with women making up the remaining 33.7%. When it came to major occupational groups, workers in elementary occupations made up the greatest percentage (19.6%) of all those engaged in gainful activity. Following in order of percentage, plant and machine operators and assemblers (13.2%) and service and sales workers (17.6%) (Philippine Statistics Authority, 2015 Census of Population, Report No. 2 – Demographic and Socioeconomic Characteristics General Santos City, June 2017)

With the abovementioned data, during the pre-pandemic, it can be noted that there were numerous learners that were engaging in gainful activities. With this pandemic, the Lanton High School Guidance Office in the year 2020 has recorded around 25 learners engaged in gainful activities or as working students. These same students were those who were still engaged in gainful activities for the purpose of aiding their families in financial aspects.

According to the results of the study by Darolia (2014), while understudies take less qualities in school due of work commitments, Filipino students are still able to sustain themselves financially through working despite having financial challenges (Abenoja, et al., 2019).

Basically, this action research will enable a positive transfer of learning for working students. This will benefit them through the program and intervention to be crafted. Finally, having this action research will address the difficulties they face in these trying times.

Research Questions

This study aimed to elucidate the education process during the COVID 19 pandemic in the lens of the working students of Lanton High School.

Specifically, it will seek to answer the following questions:

1. What is the scope of work of the working students of Lanton High School in terms of:
 - a. Schedule; and
 - b. Nature?
2. How do they view education process in the new normal?
3. What are their experiences in the new normal of education in terms of:
 - a. Module distribution;
 - b. Passing of answer sheets; and
 - c. Accomplishing the SLMs/ SSLMs?
4. What will be the possible intervention for the working students of Lanton High School?

METHODOLOGY

This research was conducted at Lanton High School- a lone high school in Barangay Apopong, General Santos City. It utilized purposive and snowball sampling as the sampling methods. The working students of Lanton High School were purposely chosen as the respondents of this action research having the one criterion- that they must be a working student. This study focused on the working students' experiences and insights during the COVID 19 educational process. The data that were needed in this study were gathered through an interview. A technique called thematic analysis was employed in this action research. It is the process of a thorough inspection of data sources gathered from the live experiences of the respondents since that the research design is qualitative in nature. A technique called thematic analysis was employed in this action research. It is the process of a thorough inspection of data sources gathered from the live experiences of the respondents since that the research design is qualitative in nature.

RESULTS

Themes	Voices of the informants
Education is Still Vital During the New Normal	<i>"Mas gusto ko pa rin mag-aral dahil ayaw kong sayangin ang aking panahon na walang ginagawa sa oras ng free time ko."</i>

	I still want to study because I don't want to waste my time.
They Can Still Pursue Their Studies Even They Are Working	<i>"...para mapadayon nako akong pag-eskwela."</i> <i>...so that I can continue my schooling.</i>
Teachers and Peers Are Part of The Learning Process Even in Distance Learning	<i>"Mas gusto ko na may mapagtatanungan din ako sa mga katanungan ko about sa mga subects."</i> I want to have somebody to ask about my queries when it comes to my subjects.

DISCUSSION

The first theme is "Education is Still Vital During the New Normal". The working students of Lanton High still believe that education is as important as living in the midst of the COVID 19 pandemic. According to UNESCO's Dr. Hamed al Hamami, "children and youth are greatly impacted from school closures, to isolation, to a persistent sense of anxiety." Learning should never cease, even in times of hardship. In order to ensure that no learner is left behind, UNESCO is dedicated to assisting the Ministry of Education and Higher Education in creating remote learning solutions and guaranteeing inclusion and equity for all students. This is why, even these working students are still fighting for living, they "want to continue studying because they do not want to waste their time by just staying at home" (Mas gusto ko pa rin mag-aral dahil ayaw kong sayangin ang aking panahon na walang ginagawa sa oras ng free time ko). They believe that even they are working, they can find time to accomplish school activities especially in answering their SLMs/ SSLMs.

Second theme that had surfaced is "They Can Still Pursue Their Studies Even They Are Working." The working students of Lanton High School even during the pandemic were engaged for survival. It is indeed that everyone during the pandemic was fighting to see another day, these working students had also been immersed to different field of work. A Philippine student's account of challenges that he has faced during the pandemic re-emphasizes the urgent need to support the enhancement of education, training, and skills development systems, ensuring young people have a smoother transition from school to work, according to a reference from the International Labor Organization (ILO, 2021). That is why, even these students were working, they really wanted to enroll themselves so that there would be a "continuity of learning" (para mapadayon nako akong pag-eskwela).

Teachers and Peers Are Part of The Learning Process Even in Distance Learning is the third theme. Working students of Lanton High School also believe that in order to have a positive transfer of learning, there must also be a collaboration with everybody. Most of them cited that they needed someone that they can ask about their queries or share some

of their ideas and insights about their subjects. (Mas gusto ko na may mapagtatanungan din ako sa mga katanungan ko about sa mga subjects.) Teachers chatted with students on social media sites like Facebook Messenger in turn. According to Sason and Kellerman (2021), students in emergency distance learning have a critical need for interaction with their teachers. The students reported different types of interaction with their teachers during the COVID-19 period. Instructional communication (Q&A) was the most popular mode of communication, mostly through social media profiles. Additionally, they proposed that "one of the biggest factors influencing students' motivation and satisfaction as well as their capacity to complete learning assignments is teacher-student interaction. They could accomplish their SLMs/ SSLMs on time because their teachers monitored them and gave a feedback. Also, they shared their ideas with their classmates through social media platform. (Nakikipagcommunicate ako sa aking guro at pati na rin sa aking mga classmates. Minsan, nagtatanong din ako sa aking mga kaklase.)

Conclusions

The scope of work of the working students of Lanton High School is mostly domestic in nature (sa balay ra man ang akong trabaho maong dili kayo bug-at para sa akoo). Tens of millions of women and girls around the world are employed as domestic workers in private households. They clean, cook, care for children, look after elderly family members, and perform other essential tasks for their employers (Mendivil, 2020). However, some of the working students are into hard manual labor specifically in constructions (whole day gyud among trabaho kay naa man ko sa construction).

In terms of their schedule of work, those who were just staying at home for work have enough time to answer their SLMs/ SSLMs. They have almost the same working schedules. They tend to work mostly at peak hours like in the morning from 5:00 am until 8:00 am; in the afternoon from 11:00 am until 1:00 pm and in the evening from 4:30 pm until 7:00 pm or even late but for certain circumstance only. Since their employers are aware of their circumstances, the work schedule is flexible, which increases the likelihood that younger women will adjust domestic time to job-related conditions (Goldscheider, 1994). For those who were working in the construction, they have a time schedule to follow. A normal time schedule for them is from 8:00 am until 5:00 pm with one (1) hour lunch break in the afternoon. They are therefore under the formal employee of a certain company that is duly recognized by the state. Team (2020) states that no worker in the Philippines is required to put in more than eight hours a day at labor. Without fail, he deserves a one-hour lunch break every day. But an employee is only expected to work from the office for a maximum of eight hours every day.

In general, most of the women working students of Lanton High School were working at home such as domestic in nature while men are into hard manual labor. Senior Research Fellows Futoshi Yamauchi and Yanyan Liu of the International Food Policy Research Institute (IFPRI) discovered that, overall, female students benefited from their education and their subsequent participation in the workforce in a new study of a school

improvement program in the Philippines. However, it seemed that the program really disadvantaged male students in their academic pursuits (Gustafson, 2018).

On delving on how the informants view the education process during the new normal, there were three main theme that had come out. These are (1) education is still vital during the new normal, (2) education is still part of life even they are working and (3) teachers and peers are part of the learning process even in distance learning.

In this new normal of education, Lanton High School offers Modular Distance Learning as a modality of learning. The experiences of the informants in the new normal of education in terms of module distribution was as difficult as surviving COVID. Basically, it was the parents of the students who claimed the SLMs/SSLMs of their students. Yet, because of these parents “work outside the vicinity of Lanton, they fail to get their child’s SLMs/SSLMs (Lanton High School Faculty & Staff, 2021). Melorin (2021) also mentioned that most parents did not obtain and retrieve the modules according to the scheduled time. So, other students got their SLMs/SSLMs themselves. Based on the document presented by the teachers, most of the working students are on time in getting their SLMs/SSLMs. These working students were those who were just engaged in domestic labor; while those who were engaged in hard manual labor were late or not on time on a specific period of time but still managed to get the SLMs/ SSLMs (makakuha ra man gihapon mi pero late na or dili gyud on time kay may trabaho pud lagi mi.)

On passing of answer sheets, the school has a system that whenever they passed their answer sheets, they could get another batch of SLM/SSLMs. So, these working students needed to pass their answer sheets so that they could afford to get another set of SLMs/SSLMs. In passing the answer sheets, the working students are on time based on the records from the advisers. Though they faced some difficulties, these are all addressed by the concerned teachers through a constant communication. This helped both the teachers and the working students to work together to achieve the target date. However, for some instances that the working students failed to submit their answer sheets (and they could not get another SLMs/SSLMs), teachers reached them out through a phone call. (Naay mga time nga ginatawagan ko ni Ma’am kay wala pa ko nahuman sa akong module tapos naa nay bago nga set sa modules.)

On accomplishing the slms/ sslms, most of the working students can accomplish their SLMs/SSLMs accordingly because they were given time by their employer. (Kasabot ra man si Sir sa akong maong ginahatagan ko niya ug time sa pag answer sa akong modules.) On the event for those who are working eight (8) hours a day, they could manage to answer it at night. (...sa gabii ra ko muanswer.) However, when they really find difficulty in answering, they would ring up a friend or a classmate. (Mayroon din akong

mga kaklaseng napagtatanungan.) By this manner, they could accomplish and pass their answers.

Recommendations

It is recommended that this research be conducted to a wide range of locale so to verify the answers of the informants. It is also advised that the school should address the problems and plight of the working students in order to give them an avenue for learning.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The appropriate conduct of the study, secrecy, and anonymity are pertinent ethical challenges in this area of research.

Participation on a voluntary basis. The opportunity to participate was given to the participants without any expectation of consequences or loss of benefits. Consequently, the rights of the participant to contribute to the body of knowledge were carefully considered and anticipated once the goal and advantages of the study were made clear to the participant. The participants in this study were not coerced into taking part in it. Participants were permitted to stop taking part in the study at any time if it made them uncomfortable.

According to the Data Privacy Act of 2012, which safeguards the fundamental human right to privacy, participants' right to privacy could not be infringed upon without their informed agreement. One approach to maintain privacy and confidentiality in this qualitative study is to provide respondents with the choice to omit their name from the survey. Additionally, confidentiality and privacy were maintained by not disclosing the informants' age and address, if applicable, any diseases. For security reasons, their identity was thus kept secret. During the course of the study, even their answers to the survey's questions were kept private and treated as confidential information.

Within the parameters of the study, potential research participants were properly informed about the goals, procedures, and advantages of the study. The respondents' consent was acquired, confirming that their involvement would be requested voluntarily. This was done in writing, outlining all the important information that needed to be shared with the respondents as well as how the survey was carried out. In order to verify that they freely consented to participate in the survey, the respondents were required to sign an inform consent form. Participants understood that their replies would be kept confidential, that their identities would not appear on the survey, and that they could withdraw at any moment.

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REFERENCES

- Abenoja, R., N., Aguilar, J., Alcasid, M., Amoguis, A., Buraquit, D., Mama, A., Pacete, J., & Pame, J. (2019, March). The Experiences of Working Students while Studying: A Phenomenological Study of Senior High School.
- Adle, C. (2020, April 01). COVID-19 and the Poverty Pandemic.
- Chang, C. L. & Fang, M. (2020). E-Learning and Online Instructions of
- Darolia, R. (2014). Working (and studying) day and night: Heterogeneous effects of working on the academic performance of full-time and part-time students.
- GAYETA, M. G. (2020). Effects of COVID-19 Outbreak on Higher
- Goldscheider, F. (1994). Flexible Work and Household: Work and Family Constraints on Women's Domestic Labor. JSTOR.
- Gustafson, S. (2018, March 13). In the Philippines, a school program shows diverging results for male and female students. IFPRI.
- International Labor Organization. (2022, January 24). Pandemic or no pandemic, young people need more skills training! ILO.Org.
- Lanton High School Faculty and Saff. (2021). The Challenges and Success Stories of the Teachers, Parents and Studentds of Lanton High School during the New Normal of Education: Basis for Capacity Building.
- Matswetu, V. S., Munakandafa, W., Munodawafa, V. & Mandoga, E. (2020). Science student teachers' challenges and coping strategies in an open and distance

- learning environment in Zimbabwe. *Makarere Journal of Higher Education*, 4(2), 125-137.
- Melorin, M. M. (2021, July 19). *MODULE DISTRIBUTION AND RETRIEVAL: A CHALLENGE*. Depedsanjuancity.
- Mendivil, E. C. (2020, July 27). *Domestic Workers | Human Rights Watch*. Human Rights Watch.
- Philippine Statistics Authority, 2015 Census of Population, Report No. 2 – Demographic and Socioeconomic Characteristic General Santos City, June 2017
- Rotas, E. E., & Cahapay, M. B. (2020). *Difficulties in Remote Learning*:
- Sason, H., & Kellerman, A. (2021). *Teacher-Student Interaction in Distance Learning in Emergency Situations*. *Journal of Information Technology Education: Research*, 20, 479–501.
- Team, T. G. (2020, July 25). *Labor Code of the Philippines*. Global People Strategist.
- Toquero. (2020). *Challenges and Opportunities for Higher Education Amid the COVID-19 Pandemic: The Philippine Context*. ERIC.
- Tsurugano, S., Nishikitani, M., Inoue, M., & Yano, E. (2021). *Impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on working students: Results from the Labour Force*
- Unesco and Education Cannot Wait Provide the Ministry of Education and Higher Education With Online Learning Material for Teachers and Students, Education Cannot Wait. (2020, May 12). *Unesco and Provide the Ministry of Education and Higher Education With Online Learning Material for Teachers and Students*. Education Cannot Wait.